

INTEGRATIVE EDUCATIONAL BLENDS AT MARITIME HIGHER INSTITUTIONS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 29

Issue 3

Pages: 383-395

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2763

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14542672

Manuscript Accepted: 11-16-2024

Integrative Educational Blends at Maritime Higher Institutions

Elenita Abellar Apas*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The study aimed to formulate an enhanced educational development program for Concord Technical Institute, Cebu City during the Academic Year 2015-2016 based on the interplay of teaching competencies such as personal qualities, teaching competencies and skills, professional efficiency, and classroom management; and the identified information indicators such as teaching methods and techniques used; student's academic performance; and school's facilities and equipment. The respondent groups were the instructors and the selected second and third-year Bachelor of Science Marine Engineering (BSMarE) and the Bachelor of Science Marine Transportation (BSMT) Students. The teaching competencies and the identified information indicators such as teaching methods and techniques used, student's academic performance, and the school's facilities and equipment were treated and it was found that there was no significant relationship. From the facts presented in the study, a conclusion was drawn that the perception of the respondent groups on the teaching competencies are not related to the identified information indicators. It is strongly recommended that the proposed educational development program being presented in this study be implemented for the Concord Technical Institute, Cebu City.

Keywords: *maritime instruction, integrative indicators in maritime instruction, descriptive survey, Philippines*

Introduction

The world is changing, so is the shipping industry which is vibrant. The shipping industry is constantly evolving and striving for increased innovation. It provides rewarding, stimulating and long-term career prospects. Today's ships are high-value assets and should therefore be entrusted to professionals with the highest caliber. The Philippines is the biggest supplier of seafarers since 1987, making the Philippines as the manning capital of the world according to the Philippine Overseas Employment Administration (POEA). It is imperative then, for a Maritime Higher Education Institutions (MHEIs) to rate and observe the teaching competencies and the teacher's professional qualifications since they need to produce globally competitive seafarers. And, producing globally competitive seafarers in the future must first, a maritime student have a good academic performance in a Maritime Higher Institutions (MHEIs).

As stipulated in the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) Vision, Mission, and Maritime Program Objectives. The vision is to be a key leader and an effective partner in transforming Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) towards producing highly competent and productive professionals through dynamic excellent and client-oriented services. Its mission is committed to giving effective central office direction and implementing programs and mechanisms to ensure affordable quality higher education accessible to all. Its objectives aim to give and equip with the necessary knowledge, understanding and proficiency to produce qualified maritime graduates.

Thus, in Pacheco's speech during the PAMI Convention last Dec. 10, 2004, requests for innovative, creative, and updated teaching and learning techniques, as well as that the maritime teachers would continually improve their professional aspects to promote active learning to the Maritime students.

As agreed by Captain Cross in his paper at the "National Congress of MET", the various computers were used directly and indirectly to promote more interest in learning in order to achieve the learning objectives and the demonstration of competencies in the teaching and learning process. Apparently of its equal significance is his influence in promoting the improvement of basic skills, understanding, work characteristics and sufficient personal adjustments of the students. As teachers, it is not focused alone on how well he talks about his subject matter but he needs to kindle the minds of the students in order to rear the thoughts and likewise allure the hearts. Furthermore, as believed by Briones (2008), the process of teaching requires a faculty member "to teach well, to engage students, and provide significant forms of student learning. To attain with this goal, a faculty member should focus on improving an integrative approach to teaching. Integrative learning blends perspectives "from disciplines, cultures, subcultures and life experiences.

As seconded by Captain Telesporo Solda as he mentioned in his column in Tinig ng Marino (2000), "The success of the Maritime Higher Education Institutions (MHEIs) depends on the mentors. The standard of the students cannot be uplifted when the institution hire inexperienced newly graduates or retired semi-senile officers as Instructors".

As a whole, it can be said that teaching is most effective to the extent that the teacher acts in ways that will enable to continually assess and enhance the teaching-learning effectiveness. School instruction should be designed to achieve the effective teaching-learning process.

As a Maritime Higher Education Institution (MHEI), Concord Technical Institute strives to achieve to be the center of excellence in Region VII as it is stipulated in its institution's vision. In this connection, it is deemed significant for the administration to ascertain detail concerns relative to the needs of the faculty member that are essential in the enhancement of their professional qualifications and competencies and to meet with the minimum standards set by the International Maritime Organization (IMO) when it comes to

institution's facilities and equipment to augment maritime student's academic performance. It is on this context that the researcher, being an educator in a Maritime Higher Education Institution (MHEI) is interested to find out the relevance of the teacher's competencies to the identified information indicators at Concord Technical Institute during the Academic Year 2015-2016. The findings of the study will be utilized as bases for an enhanced educational development program.

Research Questions

The study aimed to formulate an enhanced educational development program for Concord Technical Institute, Cebu City during Academic Year 2015-2016. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following:

1. What is the information related to:
 - 1.1. Instructors';
 - 1.1.1. age and gender;
 - 1.1.2. highest educational attainment;
 - 1.1.3. length of teaching experience and/or seagoing service;
 - 1.1.4. government eligibility;
 - 1.1.5. pertinent seminars/trainings/workshops attended;
 - 1.1.6. teaching loads per week;
 - 1.1.7. employment status;
 - 1.1.8. methods and techniques used; and
 - 1.1.9. availability of instructional materials;
 - 1.2. Students'; and
 - 1.2.1. age and gender;
 - 1.2.2. year level;
 - 1.2.3. enrolment status; and
 - 1.2.4. academic performance?
 - 1.3. School's Facilities and Equipment?
2. Is there a significant relationship between the Teaching competencies and identified information indicators?
3. What are the best practices, issues and concerns in Maritime Instruction?
4. Based on the findings, what enhanced educational development program can be proposed?

Literature Review

This study presents the related literature and studies which greatly contributes and enriched this study. This review aims to establish a theoretical foundation, highlight existing gaps in the literature, and define key concepts relevant to the research area.

Teacher's competencies. This ensures that all educators provide standards-aligned, effective and engaging instruction utilizing research-based "best practices", including the integration of instructional technology. These include knowledge of the subject matter, teaching skills, organizational and planning, communication, tests and examinations, faculty and student's relationship, and personal attributes.

This is true with Govender (2015), he stated that personal attributes are very essential onboard a vessel. These personal attributes includes the communication, self-confidence, cleanliness and mastery. This is seconded by Tanabe (1998), in an article entitled, "On Board Training and Education of Merchant Marine Officers for the Future", cited that the characteristics of sea service aboard a ship depend upon the environment, accommodation and community which they have to live and follow the system of duties and responsibilities to be performed.

Teacher's Professional Qualifications. It is considered as the backbone of the whole educational program. This This is also true with Sapong (1998), states that society today is in need of teachers of the highest caliber who can provide quality education to the young generation. Quality education is assured when teachers adhere to professionalism in teaching and aspire for continuing personal and professional growth in his field of specialization.

Student's Academic Performance. Academic Performance of a student is very important especially that the maritime institution needs to produce globally competitive seafarers. Students perceive school factors related to their academic performance including teaching competencies. Students' perceptions of their teachers, including the teaching methods and techniques, and the different treatments students receive from their teachers seem to mediate student's academic performance.

Maritime Education. The study of Bejoc (2005) stated that Quality instruction is always equated with effective teaching, adequate facilities, and instructional materials to guarantee satisfactory student performance. The efficiency among instructors in the maritime world is very crucial and that shipping industry expects efficiency in their work; thus, it should not be underemphasized that the level of instructor's efficiency affects the students' performance. However, the Dissertation study of Garcia (2005) was conducted with the purpose of evaluating the Instruction Forms of the College of Maritime Education – Naval Institute of Technology for ISO 9001: 1994 QMS for a proposed continual improvement scheme to enhance the quality assessment tools.

Methodology

Research Design

The descriptive survey technique was used in the research process. The survey technique, otherwise known as normative survey, is a fact-finding study with adequate and accurate interpretation of the Maritime Instruction at Concord Technical Institute during Academic Year 2015-2016.

Respondents

The respondent groups are: a) Instructors' and the b) Students'. The Fourteen Instructor respondents were employed during Academic Year 2015-2016 while the Second year and the Third year Bachelor of Science in Marine Transportation (BSMT) and the Bachelor of Science in Marine Engineering (BSMAR-E)., a total number of one hundred sixty student respondents involved were officially enrolled during Academic Year 2015-2016. This study used the Simple Random Sampling Technique with student respondents.

Instrument

Questionnaire. This study utilized the questionnaire in gathering data of the respondent's under study. The questionnaire consisted of the instructor respondents profile namely: age and gender, highest educational attainment, length of teaching experience and/or seagoing service, government eligibility, pertinent seminars/trainings/workshops attended, teaching loads per week, and employment status, teaching methods and techniques used and the availability of instructional materials; and as to maritime student respondents are: age and gender, course and year level, enrolment status, and academic performance.

Instructor's Evaluation by Maritime Students and by the Instructor's Themselves. This study utilized the instructor's evaluation by student and instructor's evaluation by themselves form as the approved merit system at Concord Technical Institute with document No. CTI-QF-INS-006 to determine the instructor's competencies as perceived by the maritime students and as perceived by instructors themselves with description in each statement.

Availability of School's Facilities and Equipment as perceived by both respondent groups as required by Commission on Higher Education as stipulated in the Revised Commission on Higher Education Order No. 20 (CMO 20) series of 2015 under Section 23, Section 25, Section 27 was used.

For the best practices, issues and concerns in Maritime Instruction as perceived by both respondent groups, different information were gathered from internet sources with some modifications and approval of the Researcher's Adviser.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the summary, major findings of the study, draws the conclusion and offers recommendations. The problem, null hypotheses, the research methodology, the research The findings are organized according to the order of the sub-problems.

Basic Information Related To Instructors, Students, And School's Facilities And Equipment

Table 1. Profile of the Instructors as to Age and Gender

Age Bracket	Gender					
	Male		Female		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
46 years old and above	11	78.58	2	18.18	13	92.86
41 – 45 years old	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
36 – 40 years old	0	0.00	1	9.09	1	7.14
26 – 35 years old	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
25 years old and below	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
Total	11	78.58	3	27.27	14	100.00
Average		60.5		31.8		46.15

As reflected in Table 1, majority of the respondents were 46 years old and above with responses of 13 or 92.86 percent. Only one (1) or 7.14 percent was within the range of 36 – 40 years old. The findings disclosed that majority of the respondents are in the Late Adulthood Period. On the other hand, majority of the respondents was males with responses of 11 or 78.57 percent while, three (3) or 27.27 percent are females. It implies that, Maritime profession is considered a male dominated profession and knowing that there is an increasing trend for the male instructors to be employed in the teaching profession considering that teaching is an in demand profession nowadays (www.imo.org).

Highest Educational Attainment.

As the Table 2 illustrates, majority of the respondents were Baccalaureate Degree Holder with responses of five (5) or 35.71 percent. As stipulated in the Code of Professional Teachers Article VI, Section 5. The Secretary – General of IMO E.E. Mitropoulos calls the importance of professional development in a maritime education. This implies that they'd rather go abroad to seek greener pasture than

enlisting in the academe.

Table 2. *Information as to Highest Educational Attainment*

Degree	f	%
Ph.D./Dev.Ed.D./Ed.D.	1	7.15
Master's Degree with Doctoral Units	0	0.00
Master's Degree Holder	4	28.57
BS with Master's Units	4	28.57
Baccalaureate Degree Holder	5	35.71
Total	14	100.00

Length of Teaching and Seagoing Service.

Table 3. *Teaching Experience / Seagoing Services*

Number of Years	Seagoing Services						Teaching Experience	
	Domestic		International		Both		Total	
	f	%	f	%	F	%	f	%
26 years and above	2	28.57	0	0.00	0	0.00	2	14.29
21 – 25 years	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
16 – 20 years	1	14.29	1	25.00	1	33.33	3	21.43
11 – 15 years	1	14.29	0	0.00	0	0.00	1	7.14
6 – 10 years	3	42.86	3	75.00	2	66.67	8	57.14
5 years and below	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
Total	7	100.00	4	100.00	3	100.00	14	100.00
Average	26		7		5.67		12.89	

As reflected in Table 3 as to the seagoing services, for the domestic, majority have been in the profession for 6 – 10 years with responses of three (3) or 42.86 percent while, with that of the international, majority have been in the profession for 6 – 10 years with responses of three (3) or 75.00 percent and lastly as to the teaching profession, majority are 6 – 10 years with responses of eight (8) or 57.14 percent. It implied that they have been in the profession for an average period of time and there is a need for them to be motivated in order that they would stay long in the profession that gives them the stability and satisfaction in the improvement of the standard of living.

Government Eligibility.

Table 4. *Information as to Government Eligibility*

Eligibility	f	%
LET Passers	2	14.29
Civil Service Passers	1	7.14
Marine Deck Officer	5	35.71
Marine Engine Officer	4	28.57
Others	2	14.29
Total	14	100.00

As reflected in Table 4, majority of the respondents were Marine Deck Officers with responses of five (5) or 35.71 percent.

Pertinent Seminars/Trainings/Workshops attended.

Table 5. *Pertinent Seminars / Trainings and Workshops Attended*

Particular Items	f	%
6.09 Upgrading courses for Instructors teaching Maritime Program	10	71.43
3.12 Assessor's Upgrading course	8	57.14
6.10 Deck/Engine Simulator's Course	4	28.57
Maritime English	3	21.43
Others	3	21.43

Note: This is a multiple response table

As reflected in Table 5, majority of the respondents attended trainings on 6.09 Upgrading courses for maritime Instruction with responses of 10 or 71.43 percent since it is the minimum requirement for all instructors in teaching the maritime instruction should be a 6.09 certificate holder as stipulated in the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) Memorandum Order No. 20 Series of 2015 and the MARINA.

Teaching Loads Per Week.

As reflected in Table 6 as to the teaching loads per week, there were six (6) or 42.86 percent respondents who have 10 hours and below

on the other hand, three (3) or 21.43 percent for 26 hours and above.

Table 6. *Teaching Loads Per Week*

<i>Number of Hours</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
26 hours and above	3	21.43
21 to 25 hours	1	7.14
16 to 20 hours	2	14.29
11 to 15 hours	2	14.29
10 hours and below	6	42.86
Total	14	100.00

Based on results, it is evident that the Maritime Higher Institution has a minimum requirement per week as mandated in CMO Order No. 20 Series of 2015.

Employment Status.

Table 7. *Employment Status*

<i>Particulars</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Full Time	8	57.14
Part Time	6	42.86
Total	14	100.00

In terms of employment, there were eight (8) or 57.14 percent who were full timers.

Taching Methods and Techniques Used.

Table 8. *Teaching Methods and Techniques Used*

<i>Particulars</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>
Audio-Visual	7	50.00
Lecture-Demonstration	11	78.57
Lecture-Discussion	11	78.57
Seatworks and Laboratory Exercises	10	71.43
Simulation	8	57.14

Note: This is a multiple response table

As reflected in Table 8, Lecture-Demonstration and Lecture-Discussion got the highest percentage with 11 or 78.57 percent respondents.

Availability of Instructional Materials.

Table 9. *Availability of Instructional Materials*

<i>Particulars</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Computer / Internet	8	57.14
Laboratory Equipment	9	64.29
Overhead Projector	9	64.29
Workbook / Textbook	12	85.71

Note: This is a multiple response table

As reflected in Table 9, majority of the respondents disclosed for the use of workbook/textbook with responses of 12 or 85.71 percent. This is in support in the claim of Janovsky (2015) that traditional resources which include workbook/textbook were mostly used in the classroom since it includes any supplemental reading materials.

Students' Information

Another aspect of consideration in the educational blend is the students. This is reflected in Tables 10-13.

Age and Gender.

Table 10. *Students' Age and Gender*

<i>Gender</i>	<i>BSMarE</i>						<i>BSMT</i>					
	<i>Male</i>		<i>Female</i>		<i>Total</i>		<i>Male</i>		<i>Female</i>		<i>Total</i>	
	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
<i>Age Level</i>												
Second Year:												
36 years old and above	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
31 – 35 years old	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	1	100.00	1	2.04
26 – 30 years old	4	9.30	0	0.00	4	9.30	2	4.17	0	0.00	2	4.08
21 – 25 years old	17	39.53	0	0.00	17	39.53	14	29.17	0	0.00	14	28.57
16 – 20 years old	22	51.16	0	0.00	22	51.16	32	66.67	0	0.00	32	65.31
15 years old and below	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00

Total	43	100.00	0	0.00	43	100.00	48	100.00	1	100.00	49	100.00
Third Year:												
36 years old and above	1	2.56	0	0.00	1	2.50	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
31 – 35 years old	1	2.56	0	0.00	1	2.50	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
26 – 30 years old	5	12.82	1	100.00	6	15.00	4	14.81	0	0.00	4	10.00
21 – 25 years old	15	38.46	0	0.00	15	37.50	5	18.52	0	0.00	5	12.50
16 – 20 years old	17	43.59	0	0.00	17	42.50	18	66.67	1	100.00	19	47.50
15 years old and below	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
Total	39	100.00	1	100.00	40	100.00	27	100.00	1	100.00	28	100.00

As reflected in Table 10, of the 2nd year students, majority of the BSMar-E students belonged to the age bracket of 16 – 20 years old. This implies that, this kind of course is a male dominated course.

On the other hand, with third year students, majority of the BSMarE students belonged to the age bracket of 16 – 20 years old with responses of 17 or 43.59 percent.

Enrolment Status.

Table 11. *Students’ Enrolment Status*

Enrolment Status	BSMarE						BSMT					
	Male		Female		Total		Male		Female		Total	
	f	%	f	%	F	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Second Year:												
Regular	34	79.07	0	0.00	34	79.07	41	85.42	0	0.00	41	83.67
Irregular	4	9.30	0	0.00	4	9.30	1	2.08	1	100.00	2	4.08
Regular and Working	4	9.30	0	0.00	4	9.30	5	10.42	0	0.00	5	10.20
Irregular and Working	1	2.33	0	0.00	1	2.33	1	2.08	0	0.00	1	2.04
Total	43	100.00	0	0.00	43	100.00	48	100.00	1	100.00	49	100.00
Third Year:												
Regular	30	76.92	1	100.00	31	77.50	23	85.19	0	0.00	23	57.50
Irregular	7	17.95	0	0.00	7	17.50	3	11.11	1	100.00	4	10.00
Regular and Working	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	1	3.70	0	0.00	1	2.50
Irregular and Working	2	5.13	0	0.00	2	5.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
Total	39	100.00	1	100.00	40	100.00	27	100.00	1	100.00	28	100.00

As reflected in Table 12 as to the enrolment status of the 2nd year students, majority were regular with responses of 34 or 79.07 among the BSMarE students. As to the third year students of BSMarE, majority was regular with responses of 31 or 77.50 percent and majority was males with responses of 39 or 100.00 percent. It implies that, being regular students would not be burden for them since they will be focused and follow a normal course of the program.

Academic Performance.

Table 12. *BSMarE Second Year and Third Year Academic Performance*

Year Level	Second Year			Third Year		
	Rating	f	%	Interpretation	f	%
1.0	0	0.00	Outstanding	0	0.00	Outstanding
1.1 – 1.5	0	0.00	Very Good	0	0.00	Very Good
1.6 – 2.5	43	100.00	Good	39	97.50	Good
2.6 – 3.0	0	0.00	Fair	0	0.00	Fair
3.1 – 5.0	0	0.00	Poor	1	2.50	Poor
Total	43	100.00	Good	40	100.00	Good

As reflected in Table 12, all of the second year BSMarE students have a rating within the range of 1.6 – 2.5 interpreted as Good with responses of 42 or 100 percent. This implied that, students are in their average academic performance.

Table 13. *BSMT Second Year and Third Year Academic Performance*

Year Level	Second Year			Third Year		
	Rating	f	%	Interpretation	f	%
1.0	0	0.00	Outstanding	0	0.00	Outstanding
1.1 – 1.5	0	0.00	Very Good	0	0.00	Very Good
1.6 – 2.5	48	97.96	Good	28	100.00	Good
2.6 – 3.0	1	2.04	Fair	0	0.00	Fair
3.1 – 5.0	0	0.00	Poor	0	0.00	Poor
Total	49	100.00	Good	28	100.00	Good

As reflected in table 13 as to the BSMT second year, majority obtained ratings within the range of 1.6 – 2.5 with responses of 48 or 97.96 percent interpreted as Good and same holds true with BSMT third year students with responses of 28 or 100 percent interpreted as Good. This is a good showing but there is a need for enhancement of their ratings for the promotion and interest of the students.

School's Facilities And Equipment

Table 14. *School's Facilities and Equipment*

<i>Particular Items</i>	<i>Instructor Respondents</i>		<i>Student Respondents</i>	
	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. Buildings with fire escape/alarm systems and campus security force	2.14	A	2.07	A
2. Athletic field and/or gymnasium	2.00	A	2.03	A
3. Administrative Offices (General/Executive Office, Registrar, Accounting, NSTP/ROTC, Guidance Office)	2.14	A	2.03	A
4. Medical and dental clinic	2.07	A	2.04	A
5. Toilets	2.21	A	2.01	A
6. Canteen/Cafeteria	2.21	A	2.09	A
7. Faculty room	2.36	VA	2.02	A
8. Student lounge	2.21	A	1.99	A
9. Library room	2.00	A	2.04	A
10. Library Holdings	2.00	A	1.98	A
11. Toolroom	2.07	A	1.96	A
12. Shipboard Training Office	2.07	A	1.88	A
13. Research and Extension Office	2.07	A	1.90	A
Grand Mean	2.12	Adequate	2.00	Adequate

As reflected in Table 14 as to school facilities and equipment from the instructor respondents, it obtained an average mean of 2.12 interpreted as Adequate. This means that the school facilities/equipment met the minimum requirement as prescribed by CHED.

Facilities and Laboratory Equipment for BSMarE. Table 15 shows the facilities and equipment for BSMarE in which from the instructor respondents, it obtained an average mean of 2.15. The findings implied that the school facilities/equipment met the minimum requirements as prescribed by CHED.

Table 15. *Facilities and Equipment for BSMarE*

<i>Particular Items</i>	<i>Instructor Respondents</i>		<i>BSMarE Student Respondents</i>	
	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. Drawing Table	2.14	A	2.00	A
2. Lathe Machine	2.29	A	2.19	A
3. Electric Arc Welding Machine	2.29	A	2.29	A
4. Gas Welding	2.29	A	2.23	A
5. Marine Diesel Engine	2.29	A	2.22	A
6. Marine Diesel Engine Non-Operational	2.29	A	2.12	A
7. Steam Plant	2.21	A	2.19	A
8. Refrigeration	2.14	A	2.11	A
9. Pumps/ Compressors/Separators	2.21	A	2.11	A
10. Test Instruments	2.14	A	2.07	A
11. Training Kit/Module	2.07	A	1.95	A
12. Main Switchboard	1.93	A	2.02	A
13. Process Control Simulator	1.93	A	2.14	A
14. Engine Room Simulator (ERS)	2.00	A	2.23	A
15. Personal Protective Equipment	2.07	A	2.12	A
Grand Mean	2.15	A	2.13	A

Facilities and Laboratory Equipment for BSMT. The BSMT as part of the program offering in a maritime institution needs facilities and equipment. This is presented in Table 16.

Table 16. *Facilities and Laboratory Equipment for BSMT*

<i>Particular Items</i>	<i>Instructor Respondents</i>		<i>BSMT Student Respondents</i>	
	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. Chart room: Chart Tables	1.86	A	1.88	A
2. Navigational Equipment: Marine Sextant	2.07	A	2.00	A
3. Ship's Bridge Simulator	1.93	A	2.04	A
4. GMDSS / Communication Simulator	1.93	A	2.00	A
5. Seamanship room: Work Benches	1.93	A	1.94	A

6. Seamanship room: vises for splicing	1.86	A	1.92	A
7. Seamanship room: Painting stage with Rigging	1.93	A	1.88	A
8. Seamanship room: Boatswain’s Chair	1.93	A	1.99	A
9. Personal Protective Equipment	2.00	A	1.91	A
Grand Mean	1.94	Adequate	1.95	Adequate

For the facilities and equipment for BSMT it obtained a weighted mean of 1.94 from the instructor respondents. The findings implied that the school facilities/equipment met the minimum requirements as prescribed by CHED.

Laboratory Rooms for BSMarE. Another needed area is the laboratory rooms for BSMar-E which is reflected in Table 17.

Table 17. *Laboratory Rooms for BSMarE*

Particular Items	Instructor Respondents		BSMarE Student Respondents	
	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Physics	2.00	A	1.98	A
2. Chemistry	2.07	A	1.95	A
3. Computer	2.14	A	1.84	A
4. Engine Simulator	2.21	A	2.06	A
5. Machinery Room that can house marine engine, refrigeration, electrical equipment, etc.	1.93	A	2.04	A
6. Machine Shop	2.07	A	2.01	A
Grand Mean	2.07	Adequate	1.98	Adequate

As reflected in table 17 as to the laboratory rooms for BSMarE, it obtained an average mean of 2.07 from the instructor respondents and 1.98 from the BSMarE students. Both groups obtained weighted means interpreted as Adequate. The findings implied that the school facilities/equipment met the minimum requirements as prescribed by CHED.

Table 18. *Laboratory Rooms for BSMT*

Particular Items	Instructor Respondents		BSMT Student Respondents	
	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Physics	1.93	A	1.91	A
2. Chemistry	2.00	A	1.82	A
3. Computer	1.79	A	1.86	A
4. Chart Plotting	2.07	A	1.88	A
5. Bridge Simulator covering RADAR-ARPA and ECDIS	2.00	A	1.95	A
6. Seamanship	2.07	A	1.94	A
7. GMDSS	2.00	A	1.94	A
Total	1.98	Adequate	1.90	Adequate

As reflected in Table 18 as to laboratory rooms for BSMT, it obtained an average mean of 1.98 from the instructor respondents and 1.90 from the BSMT students. Both respondent groups obtained weighted mean interpreted as Adequate. The findings implied that the school facilities/equipment met the minimum requirements as prescribed by CHED.

Respondent Groups’ Perception On The Manifestations Of The Educational Blends

Personal Qualities. One of the attribute of the Instructor which is important is the personal qualities. This is presented in Table 19.

Table 19. *Personal Qualities*

Particulars	Teacher’s Rating	2nd Year BSMarE Students’ Rating		3rd Year BSMarE Students’ Rating			2nd Year BSMT Students’ Rating		3rd Year BSMT Students’ Rating	
	WM	Int	WP	Int	WP	Int	WP	Int	WP	Int
1. Grooming										
- has an appropriate, neat and clean grooming	4.43	O	4.15	VS	4.47	O	4.22	O	4.22	O
- look best all the time	4.43	O	4.05	VS	4.39	O	4.16	VS	4.16	VS
2. Self-Confidence/enthusiasm										
- demonstrates skills smoothly with utmost confidence and zeal	4.50	O	4.02	VS	4.49	O	4.19	VS	4.19	VS
- manifest genuine enthusiasm and pride in their calling	4.36	O	3.96	VS	4.39	O	4.12	VS	4.12	VS
3. Broadmindedness/openness										
- open-minded	4.36	O	3.94	VS	4.48	O	4.19	VS	4.19	VS
- responsive and available to the	4.36	O	3.95	VS	4.45	O	4.16	VS	4.16	VS

needs of the students										
4.Articulate										
- possess oral and written proficiency	4.36	O	3.96	VS	4.34	O	4.14	VS	4.14	VS
- has a clarity of explanations in the use of the medium of instruction	4.43	O	4.03	VS	4.33	O	4.13	VS	4.13	VS
5.Model of Ethics and Moral Behavior										
- endows the appropriate and utmost ethics	4.43	O	3.93	VS	4.34	O	4.10	VS	4.10	VS
- high moral values and inculcates good work and attitudes	4.43	O	3.97	VS	4.42	O	4.09	VS	4.09	VS
6.Composure										
- shows calmness on his/her mind	4.36	O	3.96	VS	4.32	O	4.10	VS	4.10	VS
- shows good bearing and appearance in spite of any provocations	4.43	O	3.94	VS	4.44	O	4.08	VS	4.08	VS
Grand Mean	4.40	O	3.99	VS	4.41	O	4.14	VS	4.14	VS

As reflected in Table 19 as to personal qualities, all of the personal qualities as to grooming, self-confidence/enthusiasm, broadmindedness, articulate, model of ethics and moral behavior and composure obtained weighted means interpreted as Outstanding which obtained an average mean of 4.40 as perceived by the Instructors themselves and by the 3rd year BSMAR-E student respondents which obtained an average mean of 4.41 while the 2nd year BSMAR-E perceived it as Very Satisfactory which obtained an average mean of 3.99, 2nd year BSMT and 3rd year BSMT perceived it as Very Satisfactory which obtained an average mean of 4.14.

This suggests that, personal qualities are characteristics important in the teaching-learning environment for these involve human resources responsible to affect newness and its impact to today’s digital students (Katz, 2011).

Teaching Competencies and Skills. It is the ability that extends beyond the possession of knowledge and skills. As reflected in Table 20, as to the instructors’ rating, it obtained an average mean of 4.54 interpreted as Outstanding. It revealed that the respondents groups’ have different perceptions on the Teaching Competencies and Skills. Indeed, there is a need for enhancement in promoting the interest of the 2nd and 3rd year BSMT students and 2nd year BSMar-E students.

Table 20. *Teaching Competencies and Skills*

Particulars	Teacher’s Rating		2nd Year BSMarE Students’ Rating		3rd Year BSMarE Students’ Rating		2nd Year BSMT Students’ Rating		3rd Year BSMT Students’ Rating	
	WP	Int	WP	Int	WP	Int	WP	Int	WP	Int
1.Mastery of the Subject Matter										
- know well his/her subject matter thoroughly	4.50	O	4.02	VS	4.4	O	4.4	O	4.11	VS
- this is based on the principle that one cannot give what he does not have	4.43	O	3.92	VS	4.28	O	4.28	O	4.00	VS
2.Organization of lesson										
- have a good lesson plan and well-organized units of the lesson	4.50	O	3.98	VS	4.39	O	4.39	O	4.06	VS
- follow a systematic presentation of every lessons	4.64	O	4.02	VS	4.37	O	4.37	O	4.02	VS
3.Explains clearly lesson outcomes										
- able to explain thoroughly and consistently	4.64	O	3.96	VS	4.35	O	4.35	O	4.09	VS
- this concept calls for proper motivation.	4.64	O	3.88	VS	4.31	O	4.31	O	4.07	VS
4.Uses motivational techniques that elicit student’s interest										
- uses varied motivational techniques	4.50	O	3.94	VS	4.3	O	4.3	O	4.09	VS
- uses appropriate techniques to cater student’s interest	4.57	O	3.86	VS	4.24	O	4.24	O	4.07	VS
5.Relates previous lesson to the present										
- relate and utilize the previous lessons to the present lessons	4.71	O	3.96	VS	4.44	O	4.44	O	4.09	VS
- this is based on the principle of apperception	4.71	O	3.91	VS	4.43	O	4.33	O	4.03	VS
6.Use of varied teaching methodologies and techniques										

- uses, adopts and revises varied teaching methodologies and techniques	4.57	O	3.91	VS	4.38	O	4.38	O	4.14	VS
- He / She may not only limit to chalktalk or lectures only.	4.50	O	3.88	VS	4.33	O	4.33	O	4.01	VS
7.Use of Teaching aids										
- uses appropriate teaching aids, materials, and resources	4.29	O	3.88	VS	4.37	O	4.37	O	4.08	VS
-may engage students in wholesome activities and may tap whatever potentials the students have	4.43	O	3.89	VS	4.37	O	4.37	O	4.09	VS
8.Ability to answer question										
- must be proficient, expert and knowledgeable	4.50	O	3.94	VS	4.49	O	4.49	O	4.16	VS
- possess a good composure	4.36	O	3.86	VS	4.56	O	4.56	O	4.13	VS
9.Sensitive to student's academic problems and needs										
- must shows concern, understanding	4.50	O	3.94	VS	4.4	O	4.4	O	4.17	VS
- is being responsive to the student's academic problems and needs	4.64	O	3.89	VS	4.36	O	4.36	O	4.11	VS
10.Utilization of evaluation results as basis of improving instruction										
- able to make use and adopt evaluation results	4.57	O	3.94	VS	4.5	O	4.5	O	4.16	VS
- utilize efficiently the evaluation results	4.57	O	3.88	VS	4.38	O	4.38	O	4.06	VS
Grand Mean	4.54	O	3.93	VS	4.38	VS	4.38	O	4.09	VS

Professional Efficiency. This portion presents the Instructor's professional efficiency as perceived both by the respondent groups. As reflected in Table 21 as to professional efficiency as to instructors' rating obtained an average mean of 4.50 interpreted as Outstanding. On the other hand, the 2nd year BSMarE students' rating, it obtained an average of 3.93 interpreted as Very Satisfactory while, as to the 3rd year BSMarE students' rating, it obtained an average mean of 4.41 interpreted as Outstanding. On the other hand, with the 2nd year BSMT students' rating, it obtained an average mean of 4.41 interpreted as Outstanding and 3rd year BSMT students' rating obtained an average mean of 4.06 as very Satisfactory.

Table 21. Professional Efficiency

Particulars	Teacher's Rating		2nd Year BSMarE Students' Rating		3rd Year BSMarE Students' Rating		2nd Year BSMT Students' Rating		3rd Year BSMT Students' Rating	
	WP	Int	WP	Int	WP	Int	WP	Int	WP	Int
1.Attendance and punctuality										
- arrives on or before the expected scheduled time during classes	4.57	O	3.98	VS	4.49	O	4.49	O	4.00	VS
- is being present in all of his/her classes in school.	4.57	O	3.88	VS	4.45	O	4.45	O	4.02	VS
2.Professional Growth										
- allows him/herself to grow professionally	4.64	O	3.89	VS	4.41	O	4.41	O	4.11	VS
- His / Her efficient performance is a result of his educational preparation.	4.57	O	3.91	VS	4.44	O	4.44	O	4.05	VS
3.Ability in making test questions, syllabus, IG										
- is proficient in the facility of test construction, syllabus and IG	4.50	O	3.92	VS	4.31	O	4.31	O	4.09	VS
- is efficient in making test questions, syllabus and IG	4.50	O	3.90	VS	4.39	O	4.39	O	4.01	VS
4.Promptness in submitting requirements										
- submit school requirements before or on time	4.43	O	3.97	VS	4.45	O	4.45	O	4.11	VS
5.Attendance to meetings										

Research Article

- able to attend school meetings promptly	4.50	O	3.99	VS	4.42	O	4.42	O	4.10	VS
6.Participation in academic and non-academic activities										
- participate in all school's academic and non-academic activities	4.21	O	3.96	VS	4.33	O	4.33	O	4.06	VS
Grand Mean	4.50	O	3.93	VS	4.41	O	4.41	O	4.06	VS

Professional Efficiency

Classroom Management. To maintain a good classroom atmosphere, teaching-learning activities are provided. As reflected in Table 22, the instructors' rating obtained an average mean of 4.52 interpreted as Outstanding. On the other hand with that of the 2nd year BSMarE students' rating, it obtained an average mean of 3.93 interpreted as Very Satisfactory. While, the 3rd year BSMarE students' ratings obtained an average mean of 4.46 interpreted as Outstanding. On the other hand, the 2nd year and 3rd year BSMT students' rating obtained an average of 4.09 interpreted as Very Satisfactory.

Table 22. Classroom Management

Particulars	Teacher's Rating		2nd Year BSMarE Students' Rating		3rd Year BSMarE Students' Rating		2nd Year BSMT Students' Rating		3rd Year BSMT Students' Rating	
	WP	Int	WP	Int	WP	Int	WP	Int	WP	Int
1.Ability to maintain order and discipline										
- a manager and a facilitator in the classroom.	4.43	O	4.01	VS	4.49	O	4.06	VS	4.06	VS
- impose discipline and order	4.43	O	4.00	VS	4.46	O	4.09	VS	4.09	VS
2.Ability to elicit participation in class discussion										
- use effective ways to awaken the drives and motives of the students	4.50	O	3.96	VS	4.45	O	4.06	VS	4.06	VS
- is good in motivating students to participate	4.57	O	3.89	VS	4.45	O	4.05	VS	4.05	VS
3.Promptness in starting the lesson										
- quick, eager and efficient in starting the lessons	4.64	O	3.93	VS	4.4	O	4.10	VS	4.10	VS
4.Ability to use Instructor's Guide correctly										
- make use the Instructor's Guide (IG) correctly and appropriately in lesson	4.50	O	3.91	VS	4.47	O	4.09	VS	4.09	VS
5.Rapport between peers and students										
- maintains harmonious relations with one's colleagues and students.	4.57	O	3.87	VS	4.38	O	4.09	VS	4.09	VS
6.Has self – discipline in and out of the classroom										
- behave well and show good behavior	4.50	O	3.92	VS	4.49	O	4.17	VS	4.17	VS
- possess good composure and a role model of the students	4.57	O	3.88	VS	4.56	O	4.10	VS	4.10	VS
Grand Mean	4.52	O	3.93	VS	4.46	O	4.09	VS	4.09	VS

Significant Relationships Between Instructors'competencies And Identified Information Indicator

Table 23. Significant Relationship between the Perceptions on the Teaching Competencies and the Teaching Methods and Techniques Used

Teaching Methods and Techniques Used	Perception on Personal Qualities		Perception on Teaching Competencies and Skills		Perception on Professional Efficiency		Perception on Classroom Management	
	Eta	Sig	Eta	Sig	Eta	Sig	Eta	Sig
Audio-Visual	.022	.940	.023	.938	.057	.847	.106	.718
Lecture-Demonstration	.080	.785	.133	.650	.096	.745	.105	.720

Lecture-Discussion	.129	.661	.176	.546	.119	.685	.199	.494
Seatworks/Laboratory Exercises	.138	.639	.153	.601	.075	.799	.039	.896
Simulation	.123	.674	.026	.930	.182	.533	.210	.470

* is significant at .05 level

As reflected in Table 23, it was tested at .05 level of significance and there was no significant relationship between the teaching competencies and the perception on teaching methods and techniques used.

Table 24. Significant Relationship between the Perceptions on the Teaching Competencies and the School Facilities and Equipment

Teaching Competencies	School's Facilities and Equipment					
	Instructor's Perception			Student's Perception		
	Eta	Sig	Interpretation	Eta	Sig	Interpretation
Personal Qualities	.996	.242	Not significant	.661	.432	Not significant
Teaching Competencies and Skills	.984	.454	Not significant	.686	.216	Not significant
Professional Efficiency	.973	.569	Not significant	.680	.261	Not significant
Classroom Management	.946	.741	Not significant	.690	.190	Not significant

Table 24 shows the significant relationship between the teaching competencies and the perception on school's facilities and equipment and it was found out that there was no significant relationship.

Table 25. Significant Relationship between the Perceptions on the Teaching Competencies and the Student's Academic Performance

Teaching Competencies	Student's Academic Performance		
	Eta	Sig	Interpretation
Perception on Personal Qualities	.572	.917	Not significant
Perception on Teaching Competencies and Skills	.601	.772	Not significant
Perception on Professional Efficiency	.600	.777	Not significant
Perception on Classroom Management	.611	.700	Not significant

As reflected in Table 25 whether there was no significant relationship between instructors' competencies and the school's facilities and equipment. The findings signified that teaching competencies are not a factor affecting the identified information indicators.

Best Practices In Maritime Instruction

Table 26. Best Practices in Maritime Instruction n = 174

Particulars	f	%	Rank
1. Continually evaluate the effectiveness of instruction	141	81.03	1
2. Develop and implement appropriate teaching techniques	137	78.74	3
3. Implementation of curriculum revision / Outcomes – Based Education	136	78.16	4
4. Individualized program in the general education classroom	124	71.26	5
5. Maintain a regular dialogue with the shipping industries	139	79.89	2

Note: This is a multiple response

First in rank is continually evaluating the effectiveness of instruction with responses of 141 or 81.03 percent as perceived by both respondent groups. It paves the way for ensuring quality learning for the students.

Issues And Concerns In Maritime Instruction

Table 27. Issues and Concerns in Maritime Instruction

Particulars	f	%	Rank
1. Unrevised curriculum design and teaching – learning methodologies	109	62.64	2
2. Less practical orientation in teaching	90	51.72	4
3. Non – establishment programs on the faculty trainings and seminars	92	52.87	3
4. Outdated technology in terms of facilities and equipment	110	63.22	1
5. Unqualified and unexperienced faculty members	89	51.15	5

Note: This is a multiple response

As reflected in Table 27 the main issue was the outdated technology in terms of facilities and equipment obtained responses of 110 or 63.22 percent. As the study of Bejoc (2005), there should be improved and modern school facilities and upgrading trainings on instructors to promote quality education.

Conclusions

From the facts presented in this study, a conclusion is drawn that the identified indicators such as teaching methods and techniques used, student's academic performance and school's facilities and equipment are not related to the instructor's teaching competencies

that is personal qualities, teaching competencies and skills , professional efficiency, and classroom management. Thus, there are separate entities.

References

Acero, Victorina, O. et.al. (2000). Principles and Strategies of Teaching. REX Book Store

Agena, Edwin (2009). Marine Transportation and Marine Engineering Students' Attitude on Classroom Social Environment. Lyceum of the Philippines University - Batangas City, Philippines. Published Thesis

Arao, Virginia A. (2010). Basic Maritime English Applied Onboard Ship as Compliance to STCW 1995. ISBN 978-971-95193-1-7

Bagares, Gracelyn B. (2014). Congruency of Student's Academic Performance, Teaching Competencies, and Supervisory Skills. Cebu Technological University-Main Campus. Unpublished Dissertation

Bejoc, Felix (2005). Instructional Capability of Maritime Institution and the Needs Shipping Industry Towards Curriculum Enhancement. Cebu State College Of Science and Technology-Main Campus. Unpublished Dissertation

Boeree, George C. (2006). "Abraham Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs, 1908-1970." <http://webpace.ship.edu/cyboer/maslow.htm>.

Briones, Zarmie-Lis R. (2008). The Performance of the Faculty of the CSCST System in Relation to their Coping Styles, Academic Freedom, and Job Satisfaction: Proposed Enhancement towards Quality Instruction. Unpublished Master's Thesis

Bucu, et. al. (2000). Professional Characteristics of a Professional Teacher. (College Teaching in the Philippines) REX Bookstore ISBN-971-23-1469-3

Callao, Rotsenia J. (2011). Quality of Work Life, Performance and Clientele Satisfaction at Cebu Technological University, Barili Campus towards an Enhanced Human Resource Development. Unpublished Dissertation

Capt. Cross (2004), National MET Congress, PAMI. Research Journal

Chua, Liza L. (2014). Professional Qualifications, Academic Competencies of Teachers and Employability of Graduates: Enhanced Development Plan. Unpublished Dissertation

CMO Order No. 20 series of 2015. Revised Policies, Standards, and Guidelines in Maritime Education Program

Concord Technical Institute Faculty Manual

Dela Rosa, Rowena D. (2001). English for Maritime Students. Philippine. Foundation for Maritime Teaching Aids, Inc. (MARTA)

Garcia, Leomero H. (2005). Instructional Forms of the College of Maritime Education for ISO 9001: 1994 QMS of Naval Institute of Technology: Proposal for Continual Improvement. Unpublished Dissertation

Janovsky, Angela (2015). "Instructional Materials: Definition and Examples. study.com/academy/lesson/instructional-materials-definition-examples-evaluation.html

Laguador, J and Agena, E. (2013). Time Management and Teaching Performance among Maritime and Engineering Faculty Members: Basis for an Intervention Plan. Lyceum of the Philippines University-Batangas City, Philippines. Published Dissertation

Mitropoulos, E.E. IMO Secretary-General (2011). Importance of Professional Development in a Maritime Education. The Nautical Institute. www.imo.org/en/MediaCentre/SecretaryGeneral/Speeches/40th.aspx

Mojares, Juvy G. (2014). Teaching Strategies in English: The Case of Batangas State University-Malvar, Philippines. Published Thesis

Pacheco, Lydia S. (2010). The Role of Maritime Institutions in Increasing the Philippines Share of Management Level of Officers in the Global labor Market <http://www.nmp.gov.ph/uploads/Report2010.pdf>

Peter, David (2007). "Effective Teaching Quality Instruction and Professional Development." [http://quality-instruction.blogspot.com/search/label/critical %20thinking](http://quality-instruction.blogspot.com/search/label/critical%20thinking).

Quijano, Belle M. (1993). The Motivational Needs, Professional Qualifications, Socio-Economic Status of Teachers in Three Curricula of the CSCST System in Relation to Job satisfaction: Basis for a Proposed Management Program. Unpublished Dissertation

Tanabe, Y (1998). "OnBoard Training and Education of Merchant Marine Officers for the Future". Economics and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Elenita Abellar Apas

Cebu Technological University – Philippines